

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide as a Gravimetric Reagent for Vanadium(IV)

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Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide has been used to determine 6.0 to 14.0 mg of vanadium(IV) gravimetrically with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.17\%$ for 30 determinations. The green complex $\text{VO}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2$ is precipitated in the pH-range 4.0 to 5.5 adjusted with ammonium acetate (5%), and is weighed after drying it at 110° . The presence of Ag^+ , Tl^+ , F^- , I^- or sulphosalicylic acid do not interfere in the determination. Vanadium has been separated from Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} or UO_2^{2+} using sulphosalicylic acid as the masking agent, while, iodide has been used to mask Hg^{2+} and Cd^{2+} . The method is applicable for the determination of the vanadium content of chrome-vanadium steel.

VANADIUM has been determined as V_2O_5 after precipitating the metal with a number of organic reagents, but only a few of them, e.g. 8-quinolinol¹, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime² and α -nitroso- β -naphthol³ give complexes suitable for weighing directly. Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide, which has been used as a gravimetric reagent for beryllium⁴, mercury⁵ and uranium(VI)⁶ has now been employed in the estimation of small amounts of vanadium with high accuracy. Due to high selectivity in the presence of sulphosalicylic acid, vanadium content of steel samples can also be determined without prior separation.

Experimental

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide solution: The reagent was prepared in the laboratory⁴ by the condensation of ethyl benzoylacetate and *m*-nitroaniline. A fresh solution of 0.20-0.25 g in 15 ml aqueous ethanol was prepared before use.

Vanadium(IV)-solution: Vanadyl sulphate (G. R., E. Merck) was dissolved in 0.05M sulphuric acid. The metal content of the solution was determined gravimetrically using benzoylacetanilide⁷.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grade.

Procedure: A known aliquot of the stock vanadium(IV) (6-14 mg) solution was diluted to about 150 ml, the pH was adjusted to 4.0-5.5 with ammonium acetate (5%) solution and heated to about 50° . The reagent solution was added dropwise with stirring. The amount of the reagent required was approximately three times the quantity required theoretically for vanadium present. The green precipitate formed was digested on a hot water-bath for 10-15 min. with occasional stirring. It was filtered, washed first with hot water (70° - 80°) and finally with hot 20% aqueous ethanol. Vanadium was

determined by weighing the complex after drying at 110° . The conversion factor used was 0.0804. The results of these determinations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of Vanadium(IV)

V taken, (mg)	Wt. of complex (mg)	V found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
6.10	76.2	6.12	+0.32
	75.8	6.09	-0.16
9.10	113.2	9.10	nil
	113.5	9.12	+0.22
14.50	179.5	14.43	-0.48
	180.1	14.47	-0.20

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions: A known quantity of vanadium solution (VO^{2+} , 9-10 mg) was mixed with approximately four times its weight of the desired foreign metal ion. In case of iron(III) the amount taken was about eight times the weight of vanadium. Separation of vanadium from reasonable amounts of Ag^+ or Tl^+ was possible following the procedure given above, separation from uranium(VI) was effected by precipitating vanadium at pH 4.0-4.5. However, the addition of 0.5 g of sulphosalicylic acid was necessary to determine vanadium (IV) in the presence of Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , MoO_4^{2-} or WO_4^{2-} and 1 g potassium iodide was required in the presence of Hg^{2+} or Cd^{2+} . The masking agents were added prior to the addition of the reagent and the pH was maintained at 4.0-5.0. The average relative error in these determinations was $\pm 0.12\%$.

Procedure for chrome-vanadium steel: About 0.4-0.5 g of the sample of steel was dissolved by heating with hydrochloric-nitric acid mixture. Finally, the solution was heated to fumes with sulphuric acid,

cooled, taken up with 4*N* sulphuric acid and filtered. The filtrate was treated with sodium sulphite and the excess of it was removed by boiling. Vanadium was finally precipitated with benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide at pH 4.0-5.0 in the presence of 1g of sulphosalicylic acid. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Determination of Vanadium in steel

Composition of Steel	V found (%)	Rel. error (%)
V, 3.0%; Cr, 13.4%; Mn, 0.52%; Ni, 14.3%	3.03	+1.00
C, 0.45%; Si, 2.40%	2.99	-0.33

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complex: The vanadium(IV)-bis-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex is green in colour and is practically insoluble in ethanol, chloroform, benzene and ether, but has appreciable solubility in isobutylmethyl ketone and tributylphosphate. The complex is thermally stable upto 245°.

The pure complex was analysed for vanadium by converting a known weight of it to V₂O₅ and for nitrogen by modified Kjeldahl's method¹. The results V, 7.84, 7.96% (theo. 8.04%) and N 8.71, 8.79% (theo. 8.84%) indicate the formula VO(C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₂)₂.

The magnetic susceptibility, χ_m was found to be 808.9×10^{-6} cgs unit. The paramagnetic moment, μ (= 1.41 B.M.) was slightly lower than the expected

value for non-electrolytic oxovanadium complexes with five coordinated square pyramidal structure, but not low enough to indicate dimerisation. The magnetic measurements were carried out in a modified electrodynamic microbalance developed by Neogy and Lal⁸.

Effect of sequestering agents: The presence of reasonable amounts of sulphosalicylic acid (0.5 g), fluoride (1.0 g) or iodide (1.0 g) had no adverse effect on the determination of vanadium (IV).

Interference: The presence of citric acid, tartaric acid and ethylenediamine tetraacetate prevented the precipitation of vanadium(IV).

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